

Functional Transformation of (\pm)-*threo*-Aleuritic Acid : Synthesis of 5-Methyltetrazoles

P. C. SARKAR** and S. C. AGARWAL*

Lac Processing & Product Development Division, Indian Lac Research Institute (I.C.A.R.), Namkum, Ranchi-834 010

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Several reviews on the chemistry and industrial applications of tetrazoles¹ are available. Osman *et al.*² first reported the synthesis of 5-methyltetrazoles from long-chain fatty acids. With a view to increasing the economical potential of lac by diversifying the uses of its degradation products, we report herein the synthesis of 5-methyltetrazole derivatives bearing aleuritic acid residue as substituent at 1-position, starting from (\pm)-*threo*-aleuritic acid (1) (9*RS*,10*RS*,16-trihydroxyhexadecanoic acid), the principal acid constituent of lac.

Results and Discussion

(\pm)-*threo*-Aleuritic acid (1) isolated³ from shellac, was subjected to pyrolysis with ethyl orthoformate-benzoic acid according to the reported method⁴ to yield 16-hydroxyhexadec-9*E*-enoic acid (2). This was esterified and acetylated successively to get compounds 3 and 4 respectively. Compound 4 was treated with Br₂, acetonitrile and NaN₃ in the presence of AlCl₃ by the reported procedure⁵ to yield a 1 : 1 mixture of *erythro*-bromotetrazoles (5a, 5b) followed by stereospecific *trans*-addition, which on dehydrohalogenation with NaOEt yielded 5-methyltetrazoles (6a, 6b).

Experimental

M.ps. were determined in open capillaries and are un-

corrected. Ir spectra were obtained on a Bomem MB-100 FT-IR spectrophotometer, ¹H nmr spectra (CDCl₃) on a Varian EM-360 spectrometer (60 MHz; TMS) and mass spectra on a Jeol D-300 instrument. C, H and N analyses were carried out on a Carlo-Erba 1108 instrument. Samples were monitored by tlc using silica gel-G, CHCl₃ and I₂ vapour as adsorbent, eluent and visualising agent respectively. Purity of the final product was also checked on Waters Quarternary hplc system equipped with a C₁₈ RP μ Bondapak column (3.9 \times 300 mm), Waters 486 detector set at 210 nm and Baseline software, using acetonitrile at 1.5 ml/min as mobile phase. All PE refers to petroleum ether of b.p. 40–60°.

16-Hydroxyhexadec-9*E*-enoic acid (2) : Naturally occurring aleuritic acid (1) having *threo*-configuration (m.p. 96–97°, ν_{\max} 1 698, 2 370 cm⁻¹; 32.8 mmol) was subjected to pyrolysis with triethyl orthoformate-benzoic acid as per established procedure⁴. After usual workup purification, the product 2 was obtained as a semi-solid (7.9 g, 89%); ν_{\max} 2 850, 1 702 (COOH), 3 382, 962 cm⁻¹ (*trans* CH=CH); δ 1.3 (24H, br, CH₂), 2.3 (2H, t, CH₂COOH), 3.9 (2H, t, CH₂OH), 5.4 (2H, m, olefinic protons).

Methyl 16-hydroxyhexadec-9*E*-enoate (3) : A mixture of 2 (27.7 mmol) and BF₃-etherate (3 ml) was refluxed in absolute methanol for 15 min and then poured into water. After extraction with Et₂O (4 \times 100 ml), the combined extract was washed with Na₂CO₃ (10%) and dried (Na₂SO₄). The ether extract on purification on a silica gel column using petroleum ether-Et₂O (85 : 15, v/v) as eluent yielded 3 (6.0 g, 77%); ν_{\max} 3 407, 2 902, 1 732, 968 cm⁻¹ (*trans* double bond); δ 1.3 (24H, br, CH₂), 3.2 (2H, t, CH₂COOCH₃), 3.65 (2H, t, CH₂OH overlapped with COOCH₃ signal), 5.4 (2H, m, CH=CH).

Methyl 16-acetoxyhexadec-9*E*-enoate (4) : Compound 3 (21.1 mmol) was refluxed on a water-bath with Ac₂O-Py (1 : 3, v/v; 20 ml) for 45 min. Water (10 ml) was added to the mixture and refluxed for 20 min. The reaction mixture was then kept overnight. After workup, the crude acetate was chromatographed over silica gel with PE/Et₂O (97 : 3, v/v) to furnish 4 as a viscous liquid (6.1 g, 89%); ν_{\max} 2 914, 1 738, 969 cm⁻¹ (*trans* CH=CH); δ 1.3 (24H, br, CH₂), 2.1 (3H, s, OOCCH₃), 3.7 (3H, s, COOCH₃), 4.1

**Present address : Chemistry Department, Ranchi College, Ranchi-834 008.
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(2H, t, CH₂OAc), 5.3 (2H, m, olefinic protons).

(±)-erythro-*Methyl 16-acetoxy-9/10-bromo-10/9-(5'-methyl-1H-tetrazol-1-yl)hexadecanoate (5a,b)*: NaN₃ (18.4 mmol) was added in portions to a well-stirred and cooled (0°) solution of **4** (18.4 mmol), anhydrous AlCl₃ (18.4 mmol) and Br₂ (18.4 mmol) in acetonitrile (120 ml). The reaction mixture was shaken at ambient temperature for 6 h. It was then filtered and the filtrate diluted with water followed by extraction with CH₂Cl₂ (4 × 100 ml). After usual workup, a deep brown liquid was obtained which was chromatographed over silica gel. Elution with PE/Et₂O (95 : 5, v/v) yielded the dibromo addition product which gave positive Bielsstein test, ν_{\max} 1 741, 671 cm⁻¹ (C-Br). Further elution with PE/Et₂O (60 : 40, v/v) afforded a mixture of **5a** and **5b** as deep brown viscous liquid (6.8 g, 75.6%); ν_{\max} 1 741 (ester), 1 457, 1 369 (C=N, N=N), 1 240, 1 038 (tetrazole ring), 605 cm⁻¹ (C-Br); δ 2.1 (3H, s, OOCCH₃), 3.6 (3H, s, COOCH₃), 4.65 (2H, m, C₉ and C₁₀ methine protons).

Methyl 16-acetoxy-9/10-(5'-methyl-1H-tetrazol-1-yl)hexadec-9Z-enoate (6a, b): Compound **5** (10 mmol) was dissolved in 1% NaOEt (100 ml) and incubated at 60° for 2 h. It was then cooled, diluted with water, acidified with glacial acetic acid and extracted with Et₂O (4 × 50 ml). The combined ether extract was washed with water and dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄. Removal of solvent furnished the dehydrobrominated products (**6a, b**; 3.0 g, 73.0%),

(Found : N, 11.2. C₂₁H₃₆O₄N₄ requires : N, 11.4%); ν_{\max} 1 712 (ester), 1 508, 1 410 (C=N, N=N), 1 265, 1 051 (tetrazole ring), 727 cm⁻¹ (*cis* CH=CH); δ 1.2 (24H, br, CH₂), 2.1 (3H, s, OOCCH₃), 2.3 (2H, m, CH₂ to tetrazole ring), 4.1 (3H, s, COOCH₃), 6.0 (1H, m, olefinic proton); m/z M⁺ absent 143, 250, 293.

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